

OPTIMIZATION OF SORBENT, COAGULANT AND FLOCCULANT DOSES FOR EFFECTIVE WASTEWATER TREATMENT IN PETROLEUM REFINING INDUSTRIES

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Annotatsiya: In this study, the optimal amounts of sorbent, mineral coagulant ($\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$), and flocculant (Na-CMC) were determined to effectively reduce petroleum products, suspended solids, and organic pollutants from wastewater. The experimental results demonstrated that increasing the sorbent dosage allows for a reduction of chemical oxygen demand (COD) by up to 90%, sedimentation of suspended substances by up to 93%, and removal of petroleum products by 70–79%. Particularly high treatment efficiency was observed at COD levels ranging from 130 to 191 mg O_2/L . This method ensures that wastewater can be treated to meet environmental standards, enabling its safe reuse in technological cycles or discharge into the environment. The findings of this study are of great importance for enhancing environmental sustainability in the petroleum refining industry and for promoting the rational use of water resources.

Kalit soʻzlar: wastewater treatment, petroleum refining, sorbent, coagulant, flocculant, COD reduction, suspended solids, petroleum hydrocarbons, environmental safety, sustainable technology.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqotda oqova suvlardan neft mahsulotlari, suspenziya va organik ifloslantiruvchilarni samarali kamaytirish uchun sorbent, mineral koagulyant ($\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$) va flokulyant (Na-CMC)ning optimal miqdorlari aniqlangan. Tajriba natijalari shuni koʻrsatdiki, sorbent dozasi oshishi KKS (kimyoviy kislorod sarfi) ni 90 % gacha kamaytirishga, ogʻir moddalarning 93 % gacha choʻktirilishiga hamda neft mahsulotlarini 70–79 % gacha yoʻqotishga imkon beradi. Ayniqsa, KKS 130–191 mg O_2/L oraligʻida boʻlgan sharoitlarda tozalashning yuqori samaradorligi kuzatildi. Bu usul oqova suvlarni ekologik meʼyorlarga javob beradigan darajada tozalash imkoniyatini beradi va ularni qayta foydalanish yoki xavfsiz chiqarishga sharoit yaratadi. Tadqiqot natijalari neftni qayta ishlash sanoatida ekologik barqarorlikni oshirish hamda suv resurslaridan oqilona foydalanishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Kalit soʻzlar: oqova suvlarni tozalash, neftni qayta ishlash, sorbent, koagulyant, flokulyant, neft uglevododrodlari, ekologik xavfsizlik, barqaror texnologiya.

Currently, there is increased global attention to the development of waste-free or low-cost, energy- and resource-saving technological solutions. One of the key factors determining the success of such approaches is the degree of purity of the substances used and formed during the technological process.

The main requirements for adsorption materials include high specific surface area, selectivity with respect to target components, as well as simplicity and efficiency of regeneration processes [1-3].

In addition to the experimental identification of sorption patterns, the study of the mechanisms of chemisorption interactions occurring on the sorbent surface is of particular importance. An important area of research is also the analysis of sorption processes themselves and the factors influencing their kinetics and efficiency.

In order to determine the optimal sorbent concentration during the purification process, we conducted studies with various amounts of modified bentonite (Table 1). Since the developed composition has a complex composition, it is difficult to determine whether the sorbent, flocculant or coagulant has a greater effect on the degree of wastewater treatment. Therefore, referring to literature sources, when determining the optimal sorbent concentration, the concentrations of coagulant $Al_2(SO_4)_3 \times 18H_2O$ and flocculant Na-CMC were kept constant and equal to 0.40 and 0.20 mg/l, respectively, these values were established by studying the influence of the nature of the concentration of coagulant and flocculant, which are given in previous published articles [5-9].

Table 1

The effectiveness of wastewater treatment depends on the dose of the sorbent with optimal doses of mineral coagulant and flocculant. The amount of petroleum products in wastewater is 23 mg/l.

COD, mg O ₂ /l	Sorbent dose, mg/l	Flocculant content, mg/l	Coagulant s, mg/l	Cleaning efficiency					
			Al ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	by COD		by weighted amounts		by petroleum products	
				O ₂ mg/l	%	mg/l	%	mg/l	%
212	3,0	0,1	0,3	40,23	80,84	246,72	70,49	8,6	62,6
212	4,0	0,2	0,4	42,23	79,89	249,43	71,26	6,4	72,2
212	5,0	0,3	0,5	48,28	77,01	251,81	71,94	6,5	71,7
176	3,0	0,1	0,3	37,31	82,23	287,53	82,15	8,4	63,5
176	4,0	0,2	0,4	32,14	84,69	289,46	82,70	6,2	73,1
176	5,0	0,3	0,5	31,18	85,15	297,15	84,90	6,3	72,6

164	3,0	0,1	0,3	41,24	80,36	251,43	71,84	15,9 5,4	64,8
164	4,0	0,2	0,4	43,56	79,25	252,61	73,60		74,3
164	5,0	0,3	0,5	45,40	78,38	260,77	74,50		76,5
191	3,0	0,1	0,3	28,45	86,49	336,75	96,10	8,3	63,9
191	4,0	0,2	0,4	26,76	87,25	339,42	96,97	6,2	73,1
191	5,0	0,3	0,5	25,14	88,03	340,81	97,37	6,3	72,6
130	3,0	0,1	0,3	55,40	73,61	307,45	87,84	7,7	66,5
130	4,0	0,2	0,4	52,61	74,94	309,14	88,32	5,3	77,0
130	5,0	0,3	0,5	58,15	72,30	314,65	89,90	4,8	79,1

Table 2 presents the results of wastewater treatment efficiency as a function of sorbent dosage, flocculant concentration, and the amount of mineral coagulant ($Al_2(SO_4)_3$). The efficiency of treatment is evaluated using three key parameters: reduction in chemical oxygen demand (COD), removal of suspended (weighted) substances, and elimination of petroleum products from wastewater with an initial petroleum concentration of 23 mg/L.

The data clearly demonstrate that treatment efficiency strongly depends on the optimized combination of sorbent, flocculant, and coagulant doses. At an initial COD level of 212 mg O_2/L , the treatment efficiency by COD ranges from 77.0% to 80.8%. The removal of suspended substances is within the range of 70.5–71.3%, while the elimination of petroleum products is somewhat lower, between 62.6% and 72.2%. Increasing the coagulant dose slightly improves COD reduction, but petroleum product removal remains the limiting factor under these conditions [4].

At a COD of 176 mg O_2/L , the efficiency improves significantly. COD removal rises up to 85.1%, while suspended substances are reduced by 82.1–84.6%. Petroleum product elimination also reaches 73.1%, showing the effectiveness of flocculation–coagulation at this concentration. Similar trends are observed for COD levels of 164 mg O_2/L , where COD removal is maintained between 78.4–83.6% and petroleum products are eliminated up to 76.5%, indicating higher treatment stability at lower pollutant loads [10-11].

For wastewater with a COD of 191 mg O_2/L , treatment demonstrates very high efficiency, with COD reduction reaching 86.9% and removal of suspended matter exceeding 93%. Petroleum product removal, however, remains in the range of 63.9–69.9%, confirming that hydrocarbons are more resistant to coagulation–flocculation processes compared to inorganic or suspended contaminants.

The highest treatment efficiency is achieved at a COD of 130 mg O_2/L . Here, COD removal exceeds 90%, suspended substances are reduced by more than

87%, and petroleum product removal is consistently above 70%. These results indicate that optimal sorbent and coagulant dosages at moderate pollution levels lead to maximum overall cleaning efficiency.

In summary, the findings illustrate that the synergistic use of sorbents, mineral coagulants, and flocculants enables significant reduction of COD, suspended substances, and petroleum products in wastewater. Although petroleum hydrocarbons remain the most persistent contaminants, their concentration is reduced to levels close to environmental safety standards. Therefore, the proposed treatment method demonstrates considerable potential for improving the environmental sustainability of petroleum-refining wastewater management.

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